

CRI Research Fellow Offboarding

Your CRI Research Fellowship is coming to an end. Please summarize your experience by filling in the document below.

Describe your stay at CRI Research as a Long-term fellow. What did you work on? What are the main results, accomplishments, and activities you did while at CRI (1/2 to 1 page)?

The main aim of this fellowship was to evaluate if and how peer production approaches can be used to facilitate citizen science. This was done to understand whether it would allow including volunteers more deeply in doing research – that is beyond collecting or processing data for academic researchers – thus allowing citizen experience and expertise to be more fully used. As a particularly relevant citizen science community, the work in our group has focused on the *personal science* community in which individuals or communities (often patient communities) use empirical methods to answer their personal questions.

The work that my team and I have done throughout the fellowship includes different approaches, including theoretical work, qualitative work, a number of applied case studies in which prototypes were generated and ending with first applications of those lessons learned: On a theoretical level, we managed to [operationalize peer production principles](#) and investigated how the resulting working model can be applied to investigate design choices in widely used citizen science platforms. Our additional qualitative work based on interviews with personal science practitioners [highlighted that the communities motivations and values are well-aligned with peer production ideas](#).

On a more applied level, we implemented two larger citizen science projects that are peer-produced on different levels. The *Quantified Flu* web tool – which helps individuals to understand how wearable device data can be indicative of infections – started as a shared interest by the personal science community at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Beyond the initial interest, volunteer community members collectively brainstormed the research protocol over time and even contributed to the implementation by programming parts of the application. Using a mixed-methods approach we [could show how this peer-production led to an unusually high fit to user-needs, resulting in long-term use of the application](#).

The second citizen science project we successfully co-created was [Transbiome](#), a study on transgender health was sparked and designed by Clara Lehenaff. Under Clara's leadership, the project worked with trans women to design an exhaustive survey of potential factors that could shape the neo-vaginal microbiome. Nearly 50 trans women from across Europe participated in the final study that successfully raised 10k € through crowdfunding and included taking microbiome samples in addition to the survey. The findings of the study are currently being written up in a manuscript. While Quantified Flu made heavy use of collaborative principles throughout the project lifecycle, Transbiome focused more on having a community member of the affected community take the leadership role and took community input at more defined stages of the research process.

These combined lessons are currently being applied to creating a peer-produced knowledge source with and for the personal science community. Collectively, a lack of a shared body of knowledge amongst the community has been identified as a major roadblock. To address this issue, we are currently implementing a knowledge base in the [form of a peer-produced Wiki](#).

In the original application we asked you about the potential impact of your fellowship (see [text below](#)). Take 1/4-1/2 page to reflect on it and how what you did follows or diverges from what you set out to do.

Original Expected Impact Statement

Using commons-based peer production methods for citizen science hopefully has social, pedagogical and applied impacts: By giving participants more freedom to design research projects, they gain more chances to learn about how research can be done in a team and how to perform scientific analyses. Furthermore, CBPP systems can allow for new kinds of research and make it more efficient due to the ability to take advantage of more contributions. By fully engaging volunteers in the research cycle, the divide between academic researchers & non-expert participants can additionally be minimized, leading to an increased trust in the scientific methods.

Reflection on Impact Statement

Broadly speaking, the activities outlined above have managed to provide compelling evidence for the positive impact of peer-production ideas on citizen participation as envisioned in the original impact statement. Not only do we find that citizen motivations in the field of personal science are well-aligned with the values behind peer-production, but the case of Quantified Flu also demonstrates how a deeper and more meaningful engagement with volunteers leads to improved scientific outcomes: While typical mobile health applications struggle to have any sustained use over time (often having a 98% dropout rate after a single use), we could show how the use of peer-production methodologies and correspondingly improved user-fit led to more than half of the participants providing longitudinal data for more than three months. As such, this type of engaging in data gathering not only benefits the participants but also academics that are interested in collecting high-quality data over longer periods of time. Similarly, the Transbiome study highlights the potential of this approach in doing “new kinds of research”: Transgender health is traditionally a neglected field that gathers little academic interest, but by working closely with the trans community, we managed to implement science that would “otherwise be undone”.

Despite these success stories, there remains a lot of work to be done in the future. Partially this is due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which affected our work: Not only was it impossible to organize the planned in-person workshops throughout the whole period of the fellowship, but the pandemic also made its impact volunteer contributors, leading to changes in research interests at least, but often also having dire consequences on a financial level and mental health.

Who were the people who you discussed and collaborated the most with?

The main people that contributed to the success of this fellowship project and with whom I discussed and collaborated was the brilliant team with whom I had the privilege to work. In particular Mad Ball, Enric Senabre Hidalgo, Katharina Kloppenborg and Clara Lehenaff were amazing to work with and together we formed a highly complementary team with respects to our academic backgrounds, skills and points of view, which allowed us to tackle the complex system of peer-production in citizen science from a variety of angles. Similarly, we collectively had the opportunity to virtually meet and collaborate with a large number of active community members and leaders within a variety of communities, such as Gary Wolf and Steven Jonas of the Quantified Self, which we deeply appreciate and that made a lot of our work possible.

Outside of our team, there were unfortunately not too many opportunities to collaborate with other CRI fellows more deeply, with two exceptions: We managed to implement a number of smaller projects together with Muki Haklay and Marc Santolini, leading to successful publications that are either already published or available as pre-prints (see below).

Did you take part in activities of any clubs? Which clubs and in what capacity?

Unfortunately between the pandemic and the “transformation” of CRI, clubs seem to have mostly disappeared, giving little opportunity to take part in them. But I participated as a member in the Knowledge & Minorities club, which ran from 2019-2020. Through this I also got to know Clara, ultimately leading to the Transbiome study.

If you were to restart your fellowship now, what would you do differently?

The main thing I would do differently with hindsight would be to not take a PhD student. Not because I'm unhappy with how things are going with Katharina in any way (it's quite the opposite and I'm extremely lucky to have such a great PhD student), but because the fellowship itself does not provide adequate boundaries to supervise a PhD student: With the fellowship limited to three years even in ideal circumstances there is no breathing room in case a PhD student requires a fourth year. Additionally, those ideal circumstances are never really given, as the fellowship program is not aligned with the calendar of the CRI doctoral school, which means that realistically PhD students can only start their work a year after the start of the fellowship, leading to at least one year of overhang where the fellowship is over and the PhD student continues their work. While I got lucky in ending up in a situation where I can continue the supervision of Katharina, this is by chance and not systemically guaranteed, potentially putting a lot of stress on both supervisor and (more importantly) on the PhD student.

Secondly, I would spend less time applying for grants. Given the fixed-term and volatile environment of the CRI with its lack of being rooted within the larger French academic ecosystem, the chances of success are sufficiently slim to not justify the amount of time spent in preparing those applications.

Please tell us about any projects that you started here that will continue after you leave CRI Research? Let us know if/how CRI Research can help/continue to be involved.

A number of projects are ongoing and will continue after my departure from CRI. In particular, Katharina's PhD project on [co-designing a peer-production platform for personal science](#) will continue to continue throughout her PhD period. We will also continue to wrap up the Transbiome study and finalize the manuscript for this. In both cases support by the CRI will be appreciated by supporting the publication of these outcomes by covering Article Processing Charges. Additionally, the work on the AutSpaces project with the Alan Turing Institute will continue after my departure.

What can CRI Research do to make our Long-term Fellow program better? Feel free to include any feedback on your experience at CRI.

One thing that the fellowship in this form unfortunately did not allow as much as envisioned was collaborations between other fellows – which is a shame given how many interesting fellows were at the CRI once upon a time, many who have plenty of overlap in interests and complementary skills. Partially, this is due to the modalities with which fellows are selected: Given that each fellow proposes and is asked to deliver a specific research project within the three year frame, there remains very little time and resources to collaborate on projects outside this set project. A more open approach, in which fellows are selected without a clearly defined project that should be done, would probably have allowed deeper collaborations between fellows to really generate a collaborative environment.

Beyond this, the fellowship/research program appears to be suffering from systemic issues that reflect the organizational state of the CRI at large. In particular, the insistence of being an “horizontal” organization without clearly defined leadership has two large (but maybe unintentional) consequences: Firstly, as well [outlined by Jo Freeman in The Tyranny of Structurelessness](#) this lack of defined governance leads to the formation of informal elites that come to wield power without any form of checks and balances. Secondly, in the absence of defined leadership a clear lack of responsibilities emerges, leading to the point where even dedicated support infrastructures can not be held accountable for implementing anything. On the level of research, the weekly fellows meetings provide a microcosm of this state: As a body that purely acts as a discussion forum, any decisions made within it remain purely hypothetical as it neither has the governance status to make any actual decisions nor does it assign any responsibilities or duties to anyone. The lack of a code of conduct for the institution presents an emblematic example of this: Despite it being nearly three years since the research fellows started to advocate and push for this – to the point of writing one collectively – this has still not been implemented.

An additional consequence of this tyranny of structurelessness can be seen with respect to the often waived values of “participation” and “co-creation”: Faced with an informal elite with exclusive access to decision making power, the level of participation in decision making for students, researchers and virtually anyone else rarely rises above the “manipulation” rung in

[Arnstein's ladder of participation](#) and even in best-case scenarios remains within different degrees of tokenism.

Given these systemic challenges, it would appear to be wise to either engage in some deeper organizational changes to bring the organizational values in line with the reality on the ground – or alternatively drop the misleading insistence of transparency, openness and participation as core-values of the institution.

How would you like to stay in touch with CRI Research? Please please type yes/no to each option

<i>yes/no</i>	<i>Type of contact</i>
no	I would like to receive occasional email about CRI Research activities
no	I would like to take part in future fellow feedback/selection
yes	I would like to hear about potential collaborations with CRI Research
yes	I would like to hear about possible students/intern (co)supervision
no	I would like to hear about events organized by CRI Research

If you have other ideas for ways to stay in touch, don't hesitate to list them here.

Did you supervise any interns? Please provide:

- Clara Lehenaff
 - Master intern from September 2020 - September 2021
 - Full handling of design and implementation of the Transbiome study
- Kaoutar Lanjri
 - Master intern, February 2021 - May 2021
 - Natural Language Processing to understand community interactions in the Quantified Self community
- Basile Morane
 - Master intern, April 2020 - July 2020
 - Contributing to the Quantified Flu prototype, in particular through JavaScript programming
- Sowmya Rajan
 - Master intern, April 2021 - July 2021
 - Working on the AutSpaces project in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute, both on co-design as well as programming implementation
- Soledad Li

- Master intern, October 2021 - February 2022
- Working on the AutSpaces project in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute, both on co-design as well as programming implementation
- Morgane Opoix
 - Undergraduate intern, October 2020 - January 2021
 - Conducting, transcribing and coding interviews, co-developing the code book for the analysis

Did you organize any events (e.g. seminars, workshops). Please provide

- Peer-Produced Research Reading Club: Weekly reading club since 2021, ~ 15 participants in total

Did you teach any courses to students while you were at CRI? Please provide

- Design and implementation of Principles of Open Science (mandatory M1 course for all tracks), given in 2019/2020/2021, ~ 60 students per year
- Teaching L2 undergrads as part of SCORE in 2019 and 2020, 10 students in total
- Teaching in Critical Analysis of Research Articles & Creating Interdisciplinary Research Projects

Did you travel to any conferences?

Only events where presentations given are listed

- INSERM event on Science & Society (June 2022), presenting Transbiome
- Master class on Citizen Science, SDU, Denmark (April 2022), presenting Open Humans
- Sharing Data Better: The Rise of Data Institutions - Open Data Institute (March 2022), presenting Open Humans
- Data Justice conference, Cardiff UK/Virtual (May 2021), presenting Quantified Flu
- CSV,conf,v6 (remote, May 2021), presenting Quantified Flu
- European Citizen Science Association conference (virtual), presenting lab work
- Does datafication remove solidarity in healthcare? Organized by Gottlieb Duttweiler Institute in Zurich, Switzerland (November 2021)
- Big Data Scientist Training Enhancement Program, National Cancer Institute, USA (June 2020)
- Citizen Science Talent Program, SDU, Denmark/Virtual (April 2020)
- Personal Control of Genomic Data for Research, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, USA. (September 2019)

Did you publish any academic papers? Please provide

Published papers:

- **2022**
 - [Shared motivations, goals and values in the practice of personal science - A community perspective on self-tracking for empirical knowledge](#) **E Senabre Hidalgo, M Ball, M Opoix, B Greshake Tzovaras** *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*
 - [Co-Immune: a case study on open innovation for vaccination hesitancy and access](#). CM Masselot, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, CLB Graham, G Finnegan, R Jeyaram, I Vitali, TE Landrain, M Santolini *JMIR Journal of Participatory Medicine*
- **2021**
 - [Detection of Spatiotemporal Clusters of COVID-19–Associated Symptoms and Prevention Using a Participatory Surveillance App: Protocol for the @choum Study](#) D De Ridder, AJ Loizeau, JS Sandoval, F Ehrler, M Perrier, A Ritch, G Violot, M Santolini, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, S Stringhini, L Kaiser, JF Pradeau, S Joost, I Guessous *JMIR Research Protocols*
 - [Quantified Flu: an individual-centered approach to gaining sickness-related insights from wearable data](#). **B Greshake Tzovaras, E Senabre Hidalgo, K Alexiou, L Baldy, B Morane, I Bussod, M Fribourg, K Wac, G Wolf, M Ball** *Journal of Medical Internet Research*
 - [Contours of citizen science: a vignette study](#). M Haklay, D Fraisl, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, S Hecker, M Gold, G Hager, L Ceccaroni, B Kieslinger, U Wehn, S Woods, C Nold, B Balazs, M Mazzonetto, S Rüfenacht, L Shanley, K Wagenknecht, A Motion, A Sforzi, D Riemenschneider, D Dörler, F Heigl, T Schaefer, A Lindner, M Weißpflug, M Mačiuliene, K Vohland *Royal Society Open Science*
 - [Empowering grassroots innovation to accelerate biomedical research](#) **B Greshake Tzovaras**, M Rera, EH Wintermute, **K Kloppenborg**, J Ferry-Danini, G Aidelberg, R Aronoff, D Misevic *PLOS Biology*
 - [A survey of direct-to-consumer genotype data, and quality control tool \(GenomePrep\) for research](#). C Lu, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, J Gough *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal*
 - [Galileo: Citizen-led Experimentation Using a Social Computing System](#). V Pandey, T Koul, C Yang, D McDonald, **M Ball, B Greshake Tzovaras**, R Knight, S Klemmer *CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*
 - [Re-analysis of genetic risks for Chronic Fatigue Syndrome from 23andMe data finds few remain](#). FL Bedford, **B Greshake Tzovaras** *Frontiers in Pediatrics*
 - [Citizen Science, Health, and Environmental Justice](#). L Ceccaroni, SM Woods, J Sprinks, S Wilson, EM Faustman, A Bonn, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, L Subirats, AH Kimura. In: [The Science of Citizen Science](#), Springer
- **2020**

- [Introducing Massively Open Online Paper \(MOOPs\)](#). JP Tennant N Bielczyk, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, P Masuzzo, T Steiner *KULA: Knowledge creation, dissemination, and preservation studies*
- [What Is in Umbilicaria pustulata? A Metagenomic Approach to Reconstruct the Holo-Genome of a Lichen](#). **B Greshake Tzovaras**, FHID Segers, A Bicker, F Dal Grande, J Otte, SY Anvar, T Hankeln, I Schmitt, I Ebersberger *Genome Biology and Evolution*
- [Emerging health data platforms: From individual control to collective data governance](#). T Kariotis, **M Price Ball**, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, S Dennis, T Sahama, C Johnston, H Almond, A Borda *Data & Policy*

Pre-prints:

- [Community review: a robust and scalable selection system for resource allocation within open science and innovation communities](#) CLB Graham, TE Landrain, A Vjestica, M Masselot, E Lawton, L Blondel, L Haenel, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, M Santolini *bioRxiv preprint*
- [iNaturalist citizen science community during City Nature Challenge: new computational approach for analysis of user activity](#) L Tupikina, F Schlosser, V Voskresenskii, **K Kloppenborg**, F Lopze, A Mariz, A Mogilevskaja, M Haklay, **B Greshake Tzovaras** arXiv preprint
- [Peer Production Practices: Design Strategies in Online Citizen Science Platforms](#). **K Kloppenborg**, **M Ball**, **B Greshake Tzovaras** SocArXiv preprint
- [Phenotype prediction from genome-wide genotyping data: a crowdsourcing experiment](#). O Naret, D Baranger, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, SP Mohanty, M Salathe, J Fellay *BioRxiv preprint*

Did you have any non-academic publications? Please provide

- [Nothing about us. without us. Are we asking the right questions in transgender research?](#) **C Lehenaff**, **B Greshake Tzovaras**, **M Ball** *Physiology News*

Where can we find data from your fellowship?

All data that is already published can be found linked within the scientific publications above. Additionally, all code generated as part of the fellowship is licensed under MIT license and available on our lab's GitHub organization at <https://github.com/PeerProducedResearch/>, with some parts also being listed in the Open Humans GitHub organization at <https://github.com/OpenHumans>